

Identifying pathways to research impact: Using machine learning with case studies — a work-in-process report

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Abstract

In this research-in-progress report, we explore a powerful yet underappreciated research tool—case studies—for developing Theory of Change (ToC) to support strategic planning and evaluation of investments in the research, development, and innovation ecosystem. We examine a subset of 6,975 case studies submitted for the 2014 Research Assessment Framework (REF2014) as a source of evidence of the impact of research conducted in Higher Education Institutions in the United Kingdom to illustrate the utility and power of such evidence to develop a ToC to plan and evaluate the pathways to innovation from basic research. We discuss our early findings from using machine learning tools to identify such pathways and their stages from basic research to innovation. Our final objective is to explore whether it is possible to classify these pathways into a limited number of archetypes that typify forms of transformational research.

Introduction

In this report we describe our progress with using case studies to identify pathways to innovation from basic research. Our work contributes to evaluation theory by demonstrating how case studies capture the complexities of the interactions and interdependencies within and among the researchers, research, and infrastructure systems that make up the research, development, and innovation (RDI) ecosystem. Although case studies are prolific in evaluation practice, they have often been viewed as lacking scientific rigor (Flyvberg, 2006) as a source of robust transferable evidence.

Overall, this research-in-progress report focuses on one aspect of a larger methodological endeavor aimed at identifying patterns in theories of change—the patterns that represent archetypical pathways to research impact. In evaluation studies, theories of change are what form the conceptual underpinnings for describing the underlying change mechanisms of a program or project. Our work explores how case studies can be credibly harnessed to inform the development of theories of change.

As presented in Figure 1, we have adapted McKelvey’s model-centered epistemology (2004) to form the basis of our approach. In contrast to a purely deductive approach (in which theory is developed from an axiomatic base) or to a purely inductive approach (in which theory is developed from phenomena such as with interpretivist approaches), this McKelvey’s

epistemology uses models (plural) as a generative intermediary between phenomena and theory. Models (plural) function to synthesize prevailing theory with phenomenological descriptions and then subsequently employ this integrative synthesis to iterate, update, and refine theory. In our contextualization of McKelvey’s epistemology to evaluation work, we use logic models to serve as intermediaries in developing theories of change (and potentially archetypes). Consequently, our approach contrasts with traditional evaluation approaches, which either develop theories of change purely deductively or purely inductively through a case study.

Figure 1. Our broad methodological approach is derived from McKelvey’s model-centered epistemology (2004). This research-in-progress report focuses on one aspect of a larger project focused on research-to-impact archetypes: using machine learning techniques to derive research-to-impact pathways from case studies (circled in the figure).

This research-in-progress report focuses on using machine learning techniques to extract patterns of research impact from thousands of case study narratives as a step in building toward a larger objective of describing evidence-based archetypes of research pathways to impact. In the next section, we describe the case study data and the machine learning methods.

Data, methods, and findings

Data

In 1986 the United Kingdom (UK) initiated the Research Selectivity Exercise as the first national assessment of a country’s research base. At that time bibliometric analysis was yet to become the source of indicators for assessing research productivity and quality, and systematic assessments of the contribution of investments in basic research to society were far in the future.

Since then, the assessment has evolved into the Research Excellence Framework (REF) as the national vehicle for assessing the quality and role of higher education institutions (HEI) in the research, development, and innovation enterprise in the UK. Currently, the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) provides the funding and support “to build a thriving, inclusive research and innovation system” (UKRI, n.d.). Similar approaches to assessing the contributions of HEIs has been emulated in other countries (Oancea, 2019).

The Impact Case Studies were extracted from the 2014 implementation of UK’s Research Excellence Framework (REF). The Impact Case Studies play an important role in UKRI’s assessment of the social impacts of HEIs as an input into their REF2014.

The data were comprised of the 6,975 Impact Case Studies submitted for REF2014. Each case study consisted of no more than 750 words. Of these case studies we identified approximately 1400 which discussed “technological impact,” and many of these had a section titled “Pathway to Impact.” Our objective was to extract statements from each of the case studies that corresponded to six categories shown in Table 1. Two co-authors identified fifty sentences each that represented, in their judgment, sentences that describe categories 1, 4, 5, and 6.

Table 1. Six Categories of Sentences Coded in the REF2014 Impact Case Studies

Category Number	Sentence Category Description	Classification for Machine Learning Training Set
1	Pre-existing need or the problem statement	“Selected Sentences” Classifier
2	Research-derived invention	
3	Case of use of the research-derived invention to address the problem	
4	Translation, promotion, application of the adaptation of the innovation or invention	
5	Patents, production, scale-up	
6	Societal impact	“So What” Classifier

As presented in Figure 2, these sentence categories serve as the basis to develop training sets for two machine learning algorithms: the “So What” Classifier (trained on category 6 sentences) and the “Selected Sentences” Classifier (trained on category 1, 4, and 5 sentences). When linked together stepwise, these six categories form an underlying logic describing the transformational nature of the research and the pathway from basic research to innovation or invention and its eventual societal impact (for further substantiation of the notion of broader impacts, (see <https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20204/introduction>). This work-in-progress report focuses on the development of the “So What” classifier.

Figure 2. Steps in the pathway from basic research to societal impact explored in the REF2014 Impact Case Studies (n=6,975).

Methods: The “So What” classifier

The “So What” classifier is an impact classifier that indicates whether a given sentence discusses research impact. In this sense, it is like many other text classification or categorization tasks. Text classification is a supervised, machine-learning task that has the high-level objective of assigning a label or set of labels to a span of input text. This family of natural language processing (NLP) tasks includes things like sentiment analysis, authorship attribution, spam detection, or topic classification. Jurafsky and Martin (2023) provide an introduction and overview to the task and outline common approaches. Additionally, recent work has also provided a summary of past and current approaches and challenges (Li et al., 2020; Kowsari et al., 2019).

A common challenge with text classification, especially for more niche applications and datasets, is not having enough labeled data (Xu et al., 2022). One appealing application of generative models such as ChatGPT is the opportunity to create additional training data to also help with text classification (Dai et al., 2023). Since we did not have any training data, we instead used 6,975 research case studies from the United Kingdom’s Research Excellence Framework for training data. These case studies are under 750 words and include a section called “Summary of Impact,” in which researchers describe the impact of their funded work. We used the 30,394 sentences in this Summary of Impact section as training data for a binary impact classifier (i.e., “Does this sentence describe research impact or not?”). We then used another section of the case studies titled “Underpinning Research” as examples that discuss the same work/topic but did not, we hoped, discuss the impact of the work. From Underpinning Research, there were 146,397 sentences. The advantage of setting up the training and evaluation data in this way is that we did not need to create potentially very large amounts of hand-annotated, training data. Looking ahead, we would like to hand-annotate a small sample of this data so that we could validate the key assumption that these case study sections do indeed discuss (or do not discuss) impact.

Detecting ‘impact’, or at least expressed impact, seemed similar to classifying emotion. In both tasks, we need to pay attention to the topic of the sentence as well as the tone and syntax. We also thought that a transfer-learning approach, which has worked well with affect classification, would mitigate potential out-of-vocabulary words and leverage sentence structure. To this end,

we built the “So What” classifier using a relatively common approach of sentence embeddings. Word embeddings as well as sentence, paragraph, and document embeddings have become part of standard practices in text mining and NLP projects. Two key challenges in creating embeddings are how well the high-dimension vectors represent the text on a series of evaluation tasks and how efficiently the vectors can be created using large amounts of training data (Mikolov et al., 2013).

To build the sentence classifiers, we followed the sentence-BERT approach of Reimers and Gurevych (2019) by representing each sentence as a high-dimensionality vector. We used a pre-trained, hugging-face model to represent each sentence as a 768-dimension vector which can then be used to train a logistic regression classifier for predicting whether a sentence discusses impact or not. This approach requires potentially less training data and produces better results. We next split the dataset 80/20 into “train” and “evaluation” datasets with the same proportion of impact vs. research summary sentences. Because of the class imbalance, guessing ‘no impact’ for each sentence would produce an accuracy score of 82 percent. We have taken this score as a reference point even though it is not an optimal baseline because we are interested in detecting impact.

Preliminary findings for the “So What” classifier

Using all the training data, our impact classifier achieved 89.7 percent micro-averaged accuracy on held-out evaluation data. Interestingly, only as we approached 100k training examples did we begin to exceed the accuracy of the baseline. This suggests that additional and better baseline models would be valuable for gauging the sentence embeddings gains. Specifically, a bag-of-words model and word embedding model would be useful for better understanding the improvements we are seeing from sentence-BERT embeddings as well as sentence vs. word-level vector representation for this task.

Qualitative analysis of the machine-labeled sentences revealed a few promising and preliminary findings: As expected, some of the sentences in the “Summary of Impact” sections of the case study were not focused on describing impact. In a handful of examples we examined, we determined that these sentences focused instead on background project information or explanation. Because of how we created our training and evaluation data described above, these sentences likely impacted performance. One additional limitation should be noted: we estimated that roughly 18% of text would discuss impact, which may vary more across different genres and tasks.

Next steps

As a part of a more considerable effort to explore research archetypes (Figure 1), our work so far has focused on the following tasks:

- Creating a draft, literature-based model of an archetypical pathway from investments in research to their broader research and social impacts,
- Selecting the 2014 Research Evaluation Framework case study documents as examples of a variety of research to impact pathways,
- Training and testing components of the pathway model,
- Using the Technological Impact category (1397 cases, some with explicit “Pathway to Impact” sections) for manual curation to create a training set (50 sentences/step), and
- Creating and testing two classifiers (the “So What” and the “Selected Sentences” classifiers).

This research-in-progress report has highlighted one aspect of the aforementioned tasks by focusing on developing the “So What” classifier. Although more refinement is needed to characterize the limitations of our approach, our preliminary finding of 89.7 percent accuracy for the “So What” classifier is encouraging for the subsequent phases in developing the “Selected Sentences” classifier. The method for this second multiclass classifier would take a similar approach of using pre-trained SBERT embeddings paired with a logistic regression classifier. Preliminary results indicate the classifier performs reasonably well on an evaluation set—producing a 58 percent micro-averaged accuracy.

References

- Dai, H., Liu, Z., Liao, W., Huang, X., Cao, Y., Wu, Z., Zhao, L., Xu, S., Liu, W., Liu, N., Li, S., Zhu, D., Cai, H., Sun, L., Li, Q., Shen, D., Liu, T., & Li, X. (2023). AugGPT: Leveraging ChatGPT for Text Data Augmentation (arXiv:2302.13007). arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13007>
- Flyvberg, B. (2006). Five misunderstandings about case-study research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2), 219-245.
- Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2023). *Speech and Language Processing: An Introduction to Natural Language Processing, Computational Linguistics, and Speech Recognition*. <https://web.stanford.edu/~jurafsky/slp3/>
- Kowsari, K., Jafari Meimandi, K., Heidarysafa, M., Mendu, S., Barnes, L. and Brown, D. (2019). Text classification algorithms: A survey. *Information*, 10(4), p.150.
- Le, Q. & Mikolov, T. (2014, June). Distributed representations of sentences and documents. In *International Conference on Machine Learning* (pp. 1188-1196).
- Li, Q., Peng, H., Li, J., Xia, C., Yang, R., Sun, L., Yu, P.S., & He, L. (2020). A survey on text classification: From shallow to deep learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2008.00364
- McKelvey, B. (2004). Toward a complexity science of entrepreneurship *Journal of Business Venturing* 19 (3): 313-341.
- Mikolov, T., Sutskever, I., Chen, K., Corrado, G.S., & Dean, J. (2013). Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 26.
- Oancea, A. Research governance and the future(s) of research assessment. *Palgrave Communications* 5, 27 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-018-0213-6>
- Reimers, N. & Gurevych, I. (2019). Sentence-BERT: Sentence embeddings using siamese BERT-networks. arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10084.
- UKRI (n. d.). <https://www.ukri.org/> last accessed on November 22, 2022
- Xu, G., Zhang, Z., Zhang, T., Yu, S., Meng, Y., & Chen, S. (2022). Aspect-level sentiment classification based on attention-BiLSTM model and transfer learning. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 245, p.108586